

Studies on the Preparation of Apple Cider Vinegar

Tin Moe Moe Myint Zaw¹, Yu Yu Aung²

Abstract

The research work is based on the preparation of Apple Cider Vinegar (ACV) from good apples by fermentation process to produce the economical product and to replace the imported product. Apples (Chin State source) were collected from Sanpya Market, Thingangyun Township, Yangon Region. The preparation of apple cider vinegar includes both alcoholic and acetic acid fermentation. Apple cider vinegar, like other types of vinegar, contains 5-6% acetic acid. The alcoholic fermentation was carried out by using yeast (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*). Then, acetic acid fermentation was carried out by using vinegar as a starter. The processes were conducted by varying the weight of yeast, the weight of sugar and the fermentation period to obtain highest percent of acidity. The characteristics of apple cider vinegar such as pH, acidity, total solid content and alcohol percent were determined and compared with commercial grade apple cider vinegar. In this research work, the highest percent of acidity 5.10% was obtained by using 350 g of apple, 40 g of sugar, 0.3 g of yeast, 200 ml distilled water and 50 ml of starter on 6 weeks fermentation period.

Key words: Apple Cider Vinegar, Yeast (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*), starter

Introduction

Vinegar is a liquid consisting mainly of acetic acid (CH_3COOH). The acetic acid is produced by the fermentation of ethanol by acetic acid bacteria. The acetic acid concentration ranges from 4% to 8% by volume for table vinegar. Vinegar has been made and used by people for thousands of years. Trace of it has been found in Egyptian urns from around 3000 BC.

Vinegar is a staple cooking and household item. Geographic locations and the specific ingredients tend to determine the type of [vinegar](#) that is developed.

There are numerous types of vinegar. Malt vinegar, is made from grains (most commonly barley). Coconut [vinegar](#) is common in Asia and is produced through the process of fermenting coconut juice. Cane vinegar, produced from fermented [sugar](#) cane, is popular in the Philippines. There are many others, but the most widely known ones are white vinegar, mainly utilized in cooking to cleaning, and apple [cider](#) vinegar, which has gained popularity in recent times for its versatility and health benefits. All the vinegars have zero protein, fat and fibre. There are small amounts of carbohydrate and sugar, approximately 1%. Apple cider vinegar and white vinegar each contain 5% acetic acid, and balsamic vinegar 6% acetic acid. Apple cider vinegar has high levels of potassium.

Apple cider vinegar, known as ACV or cider vinegar, is made from apples that have undergone two processes of fermentation. In its final form, apple cider vinegar has a pale to medium amber color with a very sour taste.

This vinegar is used in various recipes as a dressing, marinade, vinaigrette, and [food](#) preservative. It is also utilized as an alternative medicine or nutritional supplement for conditions such as acne, allergies, arthritis, chronic fatigue syndrome, diabetes, flu, gout, heartburn, high cholesterol, and sore throat.

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Apple cider vinegar, known as ACV or cider vinegar, is made from apple

Apple cider vinegar begins as extracted apple juice from crushed apples. Bacteria and yeast are added to break the apple's sugars into alcohol – this is the first fermentation. The

second fermentation occurs when the alcohol is fermented once again to become vinegar with aerobic bacteria, which form the acetic acid and give the liquid its sour taste.

Apple cider vinegar is a very low caloric food (3 calories per tablespoon), but is packed with essential vitamins and minerals. Some of the nutrients include potassium, magnesium, fiber, amino acids, and antioxidants (cancer fighting).

Apple cider vinegar, or cider vinegar, can be classified as organic or non-organic. Non-organic apple cider vinegar is pasteurized and characterized as a clear, amber liquid. Meanwhile, the organic or non-pasteurized variety has a cloudy and congealed appearance. This is due to the “mother of the vinegar.” The “mother of the vinegar” is the result of the acetification process, and it supposedly contains all the vinegar's natural health benefits. The “mother of the vinegar” disappears as the vinegar undergoes pasteurization, thus losing all the nutrients, antioxidants, and other health benefits.

Though apple cider vinegar is very beneficial to health, many people don't exactly like its taste in an undiluted state. It is not pleasant to drink in its natural form since it is acidic. It is recommended that the vinegar should be taken diluted with water or any kind of sweetener to ease the taste and ingestion of the liquid.

Aside from its culinary and medicinal uses, apple cider vinegar is also used as a homemade household cleaner. Because it is mostly an acid, it can be used as a body deodorant and a heavy-duty jewelry cleaner. It can fend off odors, shine metals like gold, and clean up grime, grease, and dirt deposits.

Apple cider vinegar as a supplement can take various forms. The regular form is the liquid, which can be drunk with or without water or sugar. There are also apple cider vinegar pills, capsules, and tablets, which are very convenient to ingest, although there is some suspicion in terms of their quality.

Apple cider vinegar has been used to disinfect, preserve food, clear up acne, treat toe fungus, lice, warts, and inner ear infections. Vinegar has been shown to prevent [E.Coli bacteria](#) from growing and multiplying in food.

Apple cider vinegar increases the [efficiency of insulin](#) in breaking down sugar during a high-carb meal. High blood sugars, if untreated, will lead to serious health problems that effects every single organ of the body. [Apple cider vinegar can reduce blood triglycerides, cholesterol and blood pressure](#). Triglycerides causes fatty plaque along the arteries. This buildup can lead to a blockage of blood flow or a sudden rupture, causing heart attacks or strokes. Lowering of cholesterol is made possible by pectin, which is found in apples and its vinegar. Apple cider vinegar is an alkalizing food that restores the alkaline/acid balance of body. This is important because cancer cells thrive in an acidic environment.

Apple cider vinegar is a natural tonic. It has [several health benefits](#) that are supported by scientific studies in humans. However, people have also raised concerns about its safety and possible side effects.

Apple cider vinegar has been shown to delay the rate at which food leaves the stomach. This may worsen symptoms of gastroparesis and make blood sugar control more difficult for people with type 1 diabetes. Apple cider vinegar may help reduce appetite, but may also cause

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feelings of nausea, particularly when consumed as part of a drink with bad flavor. There is one case report of low potassium levels and osteoporosis likely caused by drinking too much apple cider vinegar. The acetic acid in vinegar may weaken dental enamel and lead to loss of minerals and tooth decay. The acetic acid in apple cider vinegar has caused throat burns in children. : Some medications may interact with apple cider vinegar, including insulin, digoxin and certain diuretics.

In this research, apple cider vinegar was produced from mature apples through two successive fermentation, the first one being the conversion of ethanol by yeast (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*), and the second oxidation of ethanol by starter. In this research, vinegar was used as a starting material for the preparation of apple cider vinegar.

Materials and Methods

Raw Materials

For the preparation of apple cider vinegar, sound and suitable mature apples obtained from Chin State were purchased from Sanpya Market, Thingangyun Township, Yangon Region. The yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) from Academy Chemical Shop, 28th Street, Yangon and starter and sugar were purchased from City Mart market. The distilled water was obtained from Department of Industrial Chemistry at Dagon University.

Preparation of Alcohol

About 350 g of fresh apples were washed, chopped, and crushed. Apple juice was extracted with 200 mL of distilled water by using juice extractor. The juice was filtered by thin cloth to get clear juice. About 40 g of sugar was added into the juice and the juice was poured in to the sterilized bottle. The mixture was pasteurized in an oven at 50°C for 20 min. The mixture was cooled at room temperature and about 0.3 g of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) was added into it. The bottle was covered with thin cloth and left for 3 weeks at room temperature. At this stage, the fruit juice was converted into alcohol.

Effect of Amount of Yeast on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 weeks

Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

The same procedure was carried out by varying the amount of yeast, (0.1,0.2,0.3,0.4 and 0.5g) respectively, while keeping the following variables are constant; the amount of apple 350 g, the volume of water 200mL and the amount of sugar 40 g. The results obtained are shown in Table (2).

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Effect of Amount of Sugar on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 weeks

Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

The same procedure was carried out by varying the amount of sugar, (20,30,40,50 and 60g) respectively, while keeping the following constant; the amount of apple 350 g, the volume of water 200mL and the amount of yeast 0.3 g. The results obtained are shown in Table (3).

Effect of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percent of Alcohol (Alcoholic Fermentation)

The same producer was carried out by varying the fermentation period, (7, 14 , 21 and 28 days) respectively, while keeping the following constants; the amount of apple 350 g, the volume of water 200 mL, the amount of sugar 40 g and the amount of yeast 0.3 g. The results obtained are shown in Table (4).

Preparation of Vinegar

Alcohol obtained by using the optimum condition of yeast, sugar and fermentation period was filtered and the clear solution was transferred into another sterilized bottle. About 50 mL of starter was added into it and mixture was allowed to stand on 3 weeks for the acetic acid fermentation. At this stage, all of the alcohol was converted to vinegar. Then the solution obtained was pasteurized at 67 °C for 25 min. The prepared apple cider vinegar was analyzed for the determination of total solids content, pH, alcohol content and acidity.

Effect of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percent of Acidity (Acetic Acid Fermentation)

The same procedure was carried out by varying the fermentation period, (7,14, 21 and 28 days) respectively, while keeping the following variables are constant : the amount of apple 350 g, the volume of distilled water 200 mL, the amount of yeast 0.3 g , the amount of sugar 40 g and the amount of starter 50 mL. The results obtained are shown in Table (5).

Analysis of Prepared Apple Cider Vinegar

Determination of Total Solids Content

About 10 mL of apple cider vinegar sample was placed in a previously weighed, dry, clean porcelain basin and heated to dryness. Then, it was placed on the sand bath for 30 min. After that, it was cooled for 10 min and weighed again. This procedure was repeated until a constant weighed was obtained. The percentage of total solid content of apple cider vinegar was calculated as follows.

$$\text{Total Solids Content (v/v \%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of residue} \times 100}{\text{Weight of Sample}}$$

* The results are shown in Table (1) to (6).

Effect of Amount of Sugar on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 weeks Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

The same procedure was carried out by varying the amount of sugar, (20 g, 40 g, 60g) respectively, while keeping the following constant; the amount of apple volume of water 200mL and the amount of yeast 0.3 g. The results obtained are shown in Table (3).

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Determination of pH

The pH meter (Waterproof pH Tester 20) was first standardized by placing in two known buffer solutions of pH 4 to 7. Then, the pH values of prepared apple cider vinegar were measured with this pH meter and the data obtained are shown in Tables (1) to (6).

Determination of Alcohol Content

About 10 mL of distilled water was placed in a previously weighed, dry, clean density bottle and weighed again. Then, it was placed in an oven at 115°C for 10 min. After that, it was cooled for 10 min in the desiccator. And then, about 10 ml of the sample, was placed in a dry, clean density bottle and weighed. The alcohol percentage of prepared apple cider vinegar was determined from the relation table of specific gravity and alcohol content. The data obtained are shown in Tables (2) to (6).

Calculation;

$$\text{Specific Gravity} = \frac{\text{Density of Sample}}{\text{Density of Water}}$$

* From the relation table of specific gravity and alcohol content, the alcohol content was determined.

Determination of Acidity

About 10 mL of cider vinegar sample was placed in a 250 mL of clean, dry conical flask. Then, it was titrated with 0.1 N standard sodium hydroxide solution by using phenolphthalein indicator when the end point turned pink color the acidity of sample was determined as follows:

Calculation;

$$\text{Acidity (v/v \% Acetic Acid)} = \frac{\text{Titre} \times \text{Factor} \times 100}{\text{Weight of Sample}}$$

Titre=Titrant value of 0.1 N, NaOH

Factor= 0.006005 (for acetic acid)

The data obtained are shown in Tables (1) to (6).

Determination of Sugar Content

The sugar content of apple juice was measured by the refractometer. The sugar content obtained are shown in Table (1).

Figure (1) Apple

Figure (2) Juice Extraction

Figure (3) Prepared Apple Cider Vinegar

Determination of pH

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Results and Discussion

In this research work, apple cider vinegar was prepared by fermentation of apple juice by using yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and vinegar starter. The preparation of apple cider vinegar were carried out by varying the amount of sugar, yeast and fermentation period while keeping the amount of fruit, and the volume of distilled water kept constant. The properties of apple juice and prepared cider vinegar such as pH, total dissolved solid, acidity and alcohol content were determined and the results are shown in Table (1 to 6). In Table (1), the characteristics of apple juice were well comparable with literature value.

The effect of weight of yeast on the yield percent of alcohol is shown in Table (2). In Table (2), it was observed that the maximum yield percent of alcohol 3.71% was obtained by using 0.3 g yeast. When the weight of yeast was increased to 0.5g, the yield of alcohol percent was slightly decreased to 3.69 %. So 0.3 g of yeast was selected as suitable condition.

The effect of weight of sugar on the yield percent of alcohol is shown in Table (3). In Table (3), it was observed that the highest yield percent of alcohol 3.80% was obtained by using 40 g of sugar. When the weight of sugar was increased to 60 g, the yield of alcohol percent was decreased. 40 g of sugar was chosen as suitable condition for preparation of alcohol.

The effect of fermentation period on the yield percent of alcohol is shown in Table (4). Fermentation time was varied from 7 to 28 days. Among them, 21 days fermentation period was selected as suitable condition because of fermentation period more than 21 days, the yield percent of alcohol slightly decreased to 3.77%.

The effect of fermentation period on the yield percent of acidity is shown in Table (5). In Table (5), it was observed that the maximum yield percent of acidity 5.10% was obtained by using 50 mL of starter at the acetic acid fermentation period of (21) days. When the fermentation period was increased to (28) days, the yield percent of acidity slightly decreased to 4.99%.

From the results presented in above, the most suitable conditions are 350 g of apple, 0.3 g of yeast, 40 g of sugar, 200 mL of distilled water, and 50 ml of starter at 6 weeks fermentation for highest yield percent of acidity.

The comparison of prepared vinegar and vinegar from local market and literature value are shown in Table (6). From these results it can be concluded that the properties of prepared apple cider vinegar are well comparable with properties of vinegar from market and cited with literature value.

Table (1) Characteristics of Apple Juice

Sr.No.	Properties	Sample	Literature Value
1.	Acidity (v/v%)	0.37	0.48*
2.	Total Solids Content (w/v%)	7.54	11**
3.	Sugar Content (°Brix)	6.5	16***
4.	pH	4.14	3.0-4.5***

* <http://authoritynutrition.com>> fruit juice

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Table (2) Effect of Weight of Yeast on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 weeks Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Wt. of Apple = 350 g
 Wt. of Sugar = 40 g
 Vol. of Distilled Water = 200 mL
 Fermentation Period = 3 weeks

Sr.No.	Yeast (g)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	Alcohol (v/v%)
1.	0.1	3.71	0.46	6.70	2.58
2.	0.2	3.74	0.43	6.68	3.43
3.	*0.3	3.78	0.38	5.12	3.71
4.	0.4	3.76	0.39	4.70	3.70
5.	0.5	3.76	0.39	4.60	3.69

*suitable condition

Figure (4) Variation of Weight of Yeast on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 Weeks Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Table (3) Effect of Weight of Sugar on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 weeks

Table (2) Effect of Weight of Yeast on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Wt. of Apple = 350 g
 Wt. of Sugar = 40 g
 Vol. of Distilled Water = 200 mL
 Fermentation Period = 3 weeks

Sr.No.	Yeast (g)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)
1.	0.1	3.71	0.46	6.70
2.	0.2	3.74	0.43	6.68
3.	*0.3	3.78	0.38	5.12
4.	0.4	3.76	0.39	4.70
5.	0.5	3.76	0.39	4.60

*suitable condition

Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Wt. of Apple = 350 g
 Wt. of Yeast = 0.3 g
 Vol. of Distilled Water = 200mL
 Fermentation Period = 3 weeks

Sr.No.	Sugar (g)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	Alcohol (v/v%)
1.	20	3.61	0.84	6.93	1.78
2.	30	3.73	0.79	6.88	3.31
3.	*40	3.77	0.57	5.81	3.80
4.	50	3.64	0.59	5.71	3.77
5.	60	3.66	0.69	5.32	3.60

*suitable condition

Figure (5) Variation of Weight of Sugar on the Yield Percent of Alcohol after 3 Weeks Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Fermentation Period (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Wt. of Apple = 350 g

Wt. of Yeast = 0.3 g

Vol. of Distilled Water = 200mL

Fermentation Period = 3 weeks

Sr.No.	Sugar (g)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)
1.	20	3.61	0.84	6.93
2.	30	3.73	0.79	6.88
3.	*40	3.77	0.57	5.81
4.	50	3.64	0.59	5.71
5.	60	3.66	0.69	5.32

*suitable condition

**Table (4) Effect of Fermentation Period on the Yield percent of Alcohol
(Alcoholic Fermentation)**

Wt. of Apple = 350 g
 Wt. of Yeast = 0.3 g
 Wt. of Sugar = 40 g
 Vol. of Distilled Water = 200mL

Sr.No.	Fermentation Period(days)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	Alcohol (v/v%)
1.	7	3.34	0.63	10.18	1.14
2.	14	3.50	0.55	5.78	2.16
3.	*21	3.78	0.41	5.60	3.77
4.	28	3.56	0.45	5.44	3.75

*suitable condition

Figure (6) Variation of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percent of Alcohol (Alcoholic Fermentation)

**Table (5) Effect of Fermentation Period on the Yield percent of Acidity
(Acetic Acid Fermentation)**

Vol. of Alcohol = 400mL
 Vol. of Starter = 50mL

Table (4) Effect of Fermentation Period on the Yield percent of Alcohol (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Wt. of Apple = 350 g
 Wt. of Yeast = 0.3 g
 Wt. of Sugar = 40 g
 Vol. of Distilled Water = 200mL

Sr.No.	Fermentation Period(days)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)
1.	7	3.34	0.63	10.18
2.	14	3.50	0.55	5.78
3.	*21	3.78	0.41	5.60
4.	28	3.56	0.45	5.44

*suitable condition

Figure (6) Variation of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percer of Alcohol (Alcoholic Fermentation)

Sr.No	Fermentation Period(days)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	Alcohol (v/v%)
1.	7	3.44	3.78	3.54	Nil
2.	4	3.38	4.48	3.37	Nil
3.	*21	3.11	5.10	3.25	Nil
4.	28	3.15	4.99	3.05	Nil

*suitable condition

Figure (7) Variation of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percent of Acidity (Acetic Acid Fermentation)

Table (6) Comparison of Characteristic of Prepared Apple Cider Vinegar, Vinegar from Market and Literature Values

Sr.No.	Properties	Prepared ACV	ACV from Market	Literature Values
1.	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	3.37	1.8	1.4-3.5*
2.	pH	3.11	3.53	2.4-3.5**
3.	Alcohol Content (v/v%)	Nil	Nil	0.03***
4.	Acidity (v/v%)	5.10	5.09	3.9-9.0****

* <http://www.Ncbi.nlm.gov/pubmed/19803120>

** <http://www.silvermedicine.org>apple-cider-vinegar>

*** Egan, H., Kirk, R and Sawyer, 1981.

Sr.No	Fermentation Period(days)	pH	Acidity (v/v%)	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	Alcohol (v/v%)
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Figure (7) Variation of Fermentation Period on the Yield Percent of Acidity (Acetic Acid Fermentation)

Table (6) Comparison of Characteristic of Prepared Apple Cider Vinegar, Vinegar from Market and Literature Values

Sr.No.	Properties	Prepared ACV	ACV from Market	L
1.	Total Solid Content (w/v%)	3.37	1.8	1
2.	pH	3.11	3.53	2
3.	Alcohol Content (v/v%)	Nil	Nil	(

1Estimation Cost for Small Scale Production of Apple Cider Vinegar

Basis: 100 bottle/ day

Capacity of Bottles = 500 ml

Production Day = 300 days/yr

Direct Production Cost	Amount	Cost/Unit	Total Cost (Kyat)
1.Raw Materials			
(i) Apple	22500kg/yr	K1500 /kg	33,750,000
(ii) Sugar	2400 kg/yr	K 742/kg	1,780,800
(iii) Yeast	18 kg/yr	K12000/kg	216,000
(iv) Sodium hydroxide	12 kg/yr	K11000/kg	132,000
(v) Phenolphthalein indicator	0.48 kg/yr	K800000/kg	384,000
(vi) Starter	1750 L/yr	K 964 /L	1,676,000
2. Labor			
(i) Supervisor	1No.	3000 K/person/day	900,000
(ii) Operator	2No.	2000 K/person/day	1200,000
3. Utility Cost			
(i) Electricity	15000 unit/yr	50 K /unit	750,000
(ii) Water	40000 unit/yr	20 K /liter	800,000
4. Packaging	30000 bottles/yr	150 K/bottle	4,500,000
5. Labeling	30000 bottles/yr	1 K/bottle	30,000
Total			46,129,800

Purchase Equipment Cost, P = K 1,000,000

Salvage value, L = K 10,000

Service life, n = 10 year

$$\text{Annual straight line depreciation} = \frac{P-L}{n}$$

$$= \frac{1,000,000 - 10,000}{10}$$

$$= \frac{990,000}{10}$$

$$= K 99,000$$

$$\text{Manufacturing Cost/Bottle} = \frac{46,129,800 + 99,000}{30,000}$$

$$= K 1540.96/\text{Bottle}$$

1Estimation Cost for Small Scale Production of Apple Cider Vinegar

Basis: 100 bottle/ day

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Direct Production Cost	Amount	Cost/Unit	Tota
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2. Labor			
(i) Supervisor	1No.	3000 K/person/day	
(ii) Operator	2No.	2000 K/person/day	
3. Utility Cost			
(i) Electricity	15000 unit/yr	50 K /unit	
(ii) Water	40000 unit/yr	20 K /liter	
4. Packaging	30000 bottles/yr	150 K/bottle	
5. Labeling	30000 bottles/yr	1 K/bottle	
Total			

Purchase Equipment Cost, P

= K 1,000,000

Salvage value, L

= K 10,000

Service life, n

= 10 year

Annual straight line depreciation

= $\frac{P-L}{n}$

1,000,000 -10,000

=

10

Only, raw material, labor, utilities and packaging costs were taken in to consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charged.

Conclusion

Apple contains vitamins, minerals, fiber and acids that are good for digestion system and heart health. It can be eaten as raw and also contain antioxidants that prevent several diseases. The amounts of sugar, yeast and fermentation period are mainly related to the improvement of yield percent of alcohol and acidity of the product.

In this research work, the most favorable conditions for the preparation of apple vinegar were obtained by using 350 g of apple, 200mL of distilled water, 40 g of sugar, 0.3g of yeast and 50mL of starter. In the alcoholic fermentation, yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) was used and starter was used in acid fermentation.

The suitable fermentation period was also found to be six weeks at room temperature. The quality of prepared apple cider vinegar depends on the selection of the fresh, sound and maturity of the fruit. The pH and acidity of prepared apple cider vinegar at that condition are 3.11 and 5.10%. These values are cited with literature value and comparable with vinegar from the market.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the prepared apple cider vinegar is suitable to be used in cooking, in the preparation of pickles, sauces, mayonnaise for health purpose.

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The author would to express our profound gratitude to Rector Dr. Win Naing , Pro-rectors Dr. Nu Nu Yi and Dr. Nay Thwe Kyi, Dagon University, for their permission to perform this research. I would like to thank our Professor and Head Dr. Khin Hla Mon, Department of Industrial Chemistry, Dagon University, for her support, suggestions and comments. Special thanks to Dr Yin Shwe, Professor and Head (Retd), Department of Industrial Chemistry, Dagon University, for her kind encouragement and guidance throughout this work. Thanks are also due to my colleagues at Industrial Chemistry Department for their helps and supports in carrying out this research work.

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Online Materials

- <http://www.fruit-facts/apple-nutrition/nutritinal-content.htm>
- <http://www//.webmd.com/diet/apple-cider-vinegar>

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